

The Variscan belt: a two stage collision at the birth of Pangea

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It is broadly accepted that the assembly of Pangea occurred in Carboniferous and Early Permian times, after a long stage of continental convergence that ended with the closure of the Rheic Ocean and the collision of Gondwana with Laurussia. This collision resulted in the formation of the Variscan-Appalachian-Alleghanian orogen, which extends from Europe to eastern North America and contains key information for reconstructing the amalgamation history of the supercontinent. In the Variscan belt, the early tectonothermal events are preserved in a complex suture zone that can be traced from the Iberian Peninsula to the Bohemian Massif. In the NW Iberian Massif, the Variscan suture contains a stack of terranes including two allochthonous units with continental affinity and Gondwanan provenance (Upper and Basal Units), separated by an ophiolite belt where the most common units show protoliths ages of ~395 Ma. The same terranes appear along the belt in Central and Eastern Europe, showing almost identical lithologies, chronology and tectonothermal evolution.

In the Upper Units, ~10000–12000 m of terrigenous sediments intruded by large massifs of Cambrian (~ 500 Ma) I-type calc-alkaline granitoids and tholeiitic gabbros are considered to represent a section of a Neoproterozoic–Cambrian magmatic arc on the Gondwana margin. They record a first high/ultra-high P metamorphism at ~ 410–390 Ma. The Basal Units consist of a thick sequence of Ediacaran–Early Ordovician terrigenous metasedimentary rocks intruded by Cambrian to Ordovician granitoids (calc-alkaline to peralkaline) and minor mafic igneous rocks. They were affected by a second high-P, low-to-intermediate T₁ metamorphic event at ~370 Ma. True MORB ophiolites derived from typical oceanic lithosphere are unknown in the Variscan suture: the mafic–ultramafic sequences preserved in NW Iberia have island-arc tholeiitic composition and are interpreted as generated in supra-subduction settings. Recent Lu–Hf zircon data obtained from the Early Devonian ophiolites reveal an interaction between old continental crust and the gabbroic magmas, which consequently might not represent open oceanic domains. Due to their buoyant nature, many Devonian ophiolites escaped early Variscan subduction, so they are the most common ophiolites preserved in the Variscan suture across Europe. They were accreted beneath the Upper Units during Variscan convergence at ~ 391–377 Ma.

The tectonothermal evolution of the terranes with continental affinity records two consecutive events of deep subduction affecting the most external margin of Gondwana, both developed in a context of dextral convergence with Laurussia. The two high-P events alternated with the opening of a rather ephemeral oceanic basin, probably pull-apart, in Early Devonian times. This short-lived oceanic domain is suggested as the setting for the protoliths of the most common ophiolites involved in the Variscan suture. Current ideas for the assembly of Pangea advocate a single collision event between Gondwana and Laurussia in Carboniferous times. However, the new evidence from the allochthonous terranes of the Variscan belt suggests a more complex scenario for the supercontinent assembly, with interaction between the colliding continental margins starting earlier and lasting longer than previously considered.